

Evidences of Job Search Behaviour, Waiting, Employability Skills, Change and Dissatisfaction of North-East Migrant Worker and Employer's Reciprocity in Bengaluru

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It is evident from the primary data that North-East migrant workers in Bengaluru search job widely through social networks. Job search competition was relatively low owing to the flexibility in entry and exit particularly in private sector. Largely, job waiting period was considerably short because of the flexibility in searching and choosing job. Experienced workers in particular usually sought for a specific job with certain reservation wage. Employers preferred experienced over fresher workers. Most workers do not have a continuous work. Some workers have lowered their job aspiration below their educational qualification while employers have raised the minimum hiring qualification of the workers to be employable in their establishment due to skill shortfall. Communication was the foremost skills required and demanded to consider labour as employable. Migrant workers prominently engaged in retail, hospitality and corporate job. Workers' average income was modest and earnings vary across the occupations. Workers kept on changing their job through on-the-job search as an attempt to achieve wage growth and job satisfaction. Employers also felt the same. However, most workers desire to stay on their job due to job satisfaction and employer wanted to retain their workers owing to labour productivity. Both workers and employers encountered a widespread work, workplace and organisational problems that were addressed through various mechanisms involving colleague, employers and worker's voicing dissatisfaction.

Keywords: Job search, waiting period, employability skills, dissatisfaction, North-East migrant worker, employer

Introduction

Migration of North-East (NE) people to the city of Bengaluru is a continuous phenomenon. They have migrated to the city primarily through chain migration and social networks (Marchang, 2017 & 2018) for employment and other reasons (Usha & Shimray, 2010; Gooptu & Sengupta, 2012; Marchang, 2017 & 2018). Generally,

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NE migrants in the cities were educated having some skills for employment (Usha & Shimray, 2010; Remesh, 2012; Marchang, 2011, 2017 & 2018). The propensity to migrate increases as the level of education increases (Cote, 1997). Migrants who have migrated for employment in the cities wherein wage are higher and formal jobs are concentrated. Moreover, in India, new employment opportunities were growing in selective sectors and few urban centres (Kundu, 2007). Migration is an urban affair wherein an increased large scale migration to urban centres is expected due to slow and uneven economic growth among other reasons (International Organization for Migration or IOM, 2015). Shortage of labour supply in urban centres may be addressed by migrant labour. Migration can address labour shortages and skills shortages by making migrants in the labour pool more employable (IOM, 2015).

Migrants extensively depend on social networks for migration and for job search. Social networks are extensively used by job seekers and by employers (Montgomery, 1991; Davern, 1999; Livingston, 2006; Cingano & Rosolia, 2012). The spell of unemployment is shorten when a larger share of contacts through social networks are currently employed (Cingano & Rosolia, 2012). People engage into a waiting period while searching for their job. Some waited for short and others for longer period depending on the nature of job search, aspiration, and level of education (Prasad, 1979; Visaria, 1998). Some people waited for job for a longer period of more than seven months (Krueger, Cramer & Cho, 2014). The longer an individual waits for job the harder is to find it (Sinfield, 1967; Budd, Levine & Smith, 1988; Schmitt & Jones, 2012; Krueger, Cramer & Cho, 2014). The educated people largely aspire for specific job especially in the organised sector (Callaway & Bettenhausen, 1973; Roberts, 1985; Visaria, 1998; Parthasarathy & Nirmala, 2000). The defective education system could not produce an employable labour (Watson, 1983; Roberts, 1985; Visaria, 1998).

However, a person after a long waiting for a job lowers job aspiration (Roberts, 1985; Todaro, 1991; Mitra & Verick, 2013) considering the deteriorating employability skills. Labour employability attributes include the skills, attitude, flexibility, ability and competency among others of the employees and its interaction with the employers in the labour market (Arrow, 1971; Tseng, 1972; Hodge, 1973; Becker, 1975; Bricout & Bentley, 2000; Grip, Loo & Sanders, 2004; Crossman & Clarke, 2010; Wittekind, Raeder & Grote, 2010; Misra & Mishra, 2011; Cai, 2013; Likhitkar, 2016). Employers measure the ability of labour by the level of educational qualification (Cai, 2013). Employers have raised the minimum hiring educational qualification for a job (Blaug, Layard & Woodhall, 1969; Todaro, 1991) as labour became more competitive due to an excessive increase in the supply of labour. While labour keep on switching from one job to another in an attempt for wage growth (Even & Macpherson, 2003) and to obtain their aspired wage employment. Normally, job seekers do not accept a job with a wage below their reservation wage; however, majority of job searchers accepted a job with a wage lower than their reservation wage (Blau, 1992).

However, it is assumed that NE migrant workers keep on changing their job not only for wage growth but also due to job loss and insecurity. Employers keep on changing the workforce on a regular basis for maintaining a low wage bill (Papola,

1968) remains relevant particularly where there is no job agreement system between the worker and employer.

The paper, using primarily data, provide evidences of the job search behaviour, extent of waiting for current job, flexibility in seeking for job, and employability skills of NE migrant workers in Bengaluru. It also analyses their occupation and income. Their nature and extent of job changes depending on the nature of job security and remuneration expectation, and job satisfaction or dissatisfaction due to various reasons are also discussed. These analyses are reciprocated with the view and expression of the employer in Bengaluru. Finally, a conclusion is drawn based on the evidences of the continuous nature and behaviour of job search, on-the-job search, employability skills, and others of the workers and its reaction by the employer.

Migration from North-East India

The migration trajectory of North-East people is primarily a chain migration (Marchang, 2011, 2017 & 2018). According to Census of India, migrants from the eight NE States to Bengaluru (urban agglomeration or UA) has increased rapidly from 3780 in 1991 to 6429 in 2001 and further increased to 24214 in 2011. In 2011, Assam contributed the largest share of migrants in Bengaluru with a share of 62%, followed by Manipur (16.7%), Tripura (6.2), Meghalaya (5.3%), Nagaland (4.0%), Sikkim (2.2%), Arunachal Pradesh (2.1%) and Mizoram (1.5%). NE people have increasingly migrating to the cities for employment, education and others (Marchang, 2011, 2017 & 2018). NE people have migrated increasingly and significantly for employment from a mere 16% in 1991 to 20% in 2001 and further increased to 46% in 2011 that indicates serious unemployment issues in NER. Out-migration of NE people to the cities was attributed primarily due to the growing unemployment problems among others in NER, and availability of better and diverse employment opportunities among others in the cities (Marchang, 2011, 2017 & 2018; Usha & Shimray, 2010; Remesh, 2012). NE migrants usually adjusted with job and income aspiration depending on their household economic condition (Marchang, 2017). NE migrant workers work in both formal and informal sectors such as government offices, banking, retail sectors, hospitality, BPO, teaching, etc (Marchang, 2011, 2017 & 2018; Usha & Shimray, 2010; Remesh, 2012). In Bengaluru city, a large number of NE people worked in the organised and unorganised sectors such as in hospitality, retail, BPO jobs, etc (Gooptu & Sengupta, 2012). Presently, the same structure of employment with an increase magnitude is expected in Bengaluru.

Conceptual Framework

Literatures of job search under the imperfect information on employment opportunities existed since the early 1960s. Stigler's (1962) work on labour market information acted as the basis for various theoretical models of job search. The job search theory, according to Smith (2003) explains an aspect of behaviour in the labour market in which both workers and firms (employers) have incomplete information about the labour market opportunities. Workers, both employed or unemployed, search for job vacancies and wage offers; while employers search for workers having different labour

productivity where information is imperfect and costly to acquire. The job search theory, as per Borjas (2005), indicates that unemployment, frictional in particular, exists even if there were no fundamental difference between the supply of and demand for workers as different firms (or employers) offer different job opportunities and as workers were unaware of the location of best jobs. Thus, it takes time to find the available job opportunities in general and best job opportunities in particular. Job search activities may be over one time search (Borjas, 2005; Smith, 2003) until expected job is obtained.

Smith (2003) expressed that the aim of job search is to benefit from finding and obtaining a satisfactory job for the unemployed or a better job for the employed job searcher against the search costs. Job search costs include both direct costs such as stationary, postage, interview clothing, fares and others; and indirect costs such as the opportunities forgone. Job search is also affected by the searcher's skill, attitude to risk and time preference. The job searcher has to decide the extent and intense of job search by considering possible benefits over costs of job search. This determines the waiting period, flexibility and mobility of job search. The length of waiting period for job has a negative relationship with the reservation wage of the job searchers (Barnes, 1975; Stephenson, 1976). Reservation or expected wage is influenced by the level of human capital that affects the labour employability and job waiting period.

According to Borjas (2005) the job searchers may choose from among many different job offers as different firms (employers) make different wage offers for the same type of work to the same job seeker. These wage differentials for the same work encourage the job searchers to continue searching activity until they finds a better wage job offer. This search activity prolong the duration of the unemployment spell or the waiting period for job as it takes time to learn and locate the job opportunities provided by different employers. Some job seekers may endure a longer (or long term) unemployment spell to find a higher-paying job but may end up otherwise. Unemployment for a relatively long period of seven months or longer is the long term unemployment (Krueger, Cramer & Cho, 2014). The long term unemployed have a lower probability of finding a job due to their skill erosion or employer's discrimination against them (Sinfield, 1967; Budd, Levine & Smith, 1988; Schmitt & Jones, 2012; Krueger, Cramer & Cho, 2014).

Job seekers use social networks (friends or relatives), apply directly to the employer or through employment agencies or newspaper advertisement (Holzer, 1988; Borjas, 2005). Moreover, microlevel mobility research argues that job mobility depend on the job seeker's social network in which job seekers find better jobs through contact with superior knowledge and influence (Wegener, 1991). The job mobility arises with the job instability (Papola, 1968; Bernhardt, Morris, Handcock & Scott, 1999). Job mobility is due to the employers' policies of constantly changing the workforce to maintain low wage bills (Papola, 1968) that are primarily related to low wage issues. For workers the job changes are the mechanism for wage growth (Bernhardt, Morris, Handcock & Scott, 1999; Even & Macpherson, 2003). Most importantly, job mobility determines the labour employability (Wittekind, Raeder & Grote, 2010). Conversely, labour employability also induces job mobility. The skilled job searchers

have a strong wage bargaining power (Cahuc, Vinay & Robin, 2006) owing to their employability skills and chances of getting multiple job offers with different levels of wage. The high skilled workers have a modestly positive bargaining power; however, there was no significant wage bargaining power among the intermediate and low-skilled workers. This shows that the level of possession of employability skills determines the degree of wage received or employment offerings. Workers having low in job satisfaction have a higher probability of leaving their job (Wright & Bonett, 1992; Wright & Huang, 2012). Workers also search for alternative job while on-the-job because of job dissatisfaction (Spencer, 1986) caused by job insecurity and low remuneration (Kim, 2010).

Hence, the approach of the present study is to examine the job search behaviour that affects the waiting period for job depending on the human capital particularly the labour employability skills gained from education or prior work, and also affects the job mobility owing to the job dissatisfactions.

Data Source and Method

The study is descriptive but qualifies quantitative and qualitative aspects largely using primary data. A primary field data was collected through a field survey during August and September 2018 with a reference period of one year preceding the date of the survey in urban Bengaluru. Separate sets of semi-structured questionnaire for worker (i.e. currently employed) and employer were formulated based on the existing literature, perceptions, opinions and knowledge, and used in the survey. An employer is a person who either directly employs a worker or involves in the recruitment of worker in his/her establishment or business. A personal interview method was adopted for data collection.

The study focuses on the NE migrant workers in Bengaluru primary due to their inherent phenomenon of migration from a distant place of NE who have strong social network derived from a inviolable community bonding that may facilitate in job search process and, presumptuously, are working in informal sector having a job opportunity information for job mobility. The sample population were migrant workers from North-East India currently working in Bengaluru. NE migrants in particular migrated to Bengaluru, a fast growing megacity providing ample of job opportunities, for securing and enhancing their economic well-being through employment. For drawing it, a mixed-method of sampling technique consisting of a simple random sampling and snowball sampling was adopted due to a difficulty in locating, reaching and identifying a worker. Sample population of a worker include 255 workers who were willing to participate in the survey. Out of which 150 workers were randomly drawn from various workplaces such as salon, mall, restaurant, music institution, educational institutions; at their home; and also from NE community functions, meetings and Church in Bengaluru. And the rest 105 sample workers were drawn following Goodman's (1961) snowball sampling technique. Sample comprises largely from Manipur (31.8%), followed by Nagaland (20.0%), Assam (12.5%), Mizoram (11.0%), Meghalaya (8.2%), Tripura (6.7%), Arunachal Pradesh (5.5%) and Sikkim (4.3%).

And for selection of sample employer, initially the investigator contacted the employees of the establishments or business such as retail, spa, salon, restaurant, clinic and educational institution in Bengaluru randomly from whom the contact numbers of employers were collected. Later, such employers were contacted personally and took an appointment for participation in the survey as respondents. However, many of them refused to participate instantly as they cannot spare time for the survey. With great difficulties in finding, locating, meeting and convincing to participate in the survey eventually only 16 employers willingly participated and surveyed at their offices. Among these respondents, few (31%) were from NE who owns spa, salon, restaurant and others and the majority (69%) of them were non-NE people.

Using the primary statistical data result, the study examines the nature of job search of a person with their possessed skills to obtain their aspired job and engage in it with satisfaction. The data includes the job-seeking behaviour, employability skills, occupation, income, job change, and job satisfaction among others of a worker and its reciprocity by the employer.

Characteristics of Worker and Employer

Migration is to maximise migrants' social and economic welfare (Faggian & McCann, 2006) and to accomplish utmost individual satisfaction through obtaining better job (Santhapparaj, 1996). Chain migration takes place as relatives or some known persons were already there in Bengaluru when they migrated to it. In India chain migration is prominent through social networks (Greenwood, 1973; Banerjee, 1983; Marchang, 2018). Under social networks, the former migrants provide information about their migration destination and job opportunities to the potential migrants. Thus the potential migrants, including the NE migrants, make a decision for migration based on the available job opportunities information to enhance their economic welfare. Evidence showed that many NE people have migrated in the city of Bengaluru largely as chain-migrants (92%) for social and economic pursuit. This indicates that the new migrants, particularly the poor or relatives, were not only facilitated to migrate but also provided food and shelter temporarily until they obtain a job by the previous migrants because of their strong community or social bondings. Moreover, the parents of NE migrants were unlikely to discriminate their children on the basis of gender for migration as the sample consisted of both males (50.6%) and females (49.4%) representation.

The propensity to migrate increases as the educational qualifications increases in search of better jobs (Friedlander & Roshier, 1966; Cote, 1997) applies to the NE migrant workers as around 94% of them were educated. Most of the NE migrant workers were in their prime age with a mean age of 28 years, living in a rented house (84%) and never married bachelors (77%) being energetic, flexible and having a high job expectation. This is similar to the findings of Marchang (2011, 2017 & 2018), Usha and Shimray (2010) and Remesh (2012) that migrants from NE in the cities of Delhi or Bengaluru were mostly youth and educated. Following Blaug, Layard and Woodhall (1969) and NSSO (2014) educated persons are those who have completed a general educational level matriculation and above. Educated people are

relatively more employable than others. Education provides marketable skill and abilities necessary to job performance as a result highly educated people have a higher chance of getting a better job opportunities (Cai, 2013) is also expected for the NE migrants. Increase in the level of education enhances the skills, knowledge, ability, capability, employability and also job aspirations. Labour employability manifest recognition of Becker's (1975) human capital theory that attempt to promote the growth of the stock of human capital through the state machinery. In which investment on education and training is the function for future income earning and employment. Moreover, labour employability is well related to labour discrimination that was postulated by Arrow (1971) based on tastes of employer that reflected to wage differences and on the perception of reality relating to productivity, race, gender or school diplomas.

Evidently, majority of the migrant workers studied arts and humanities subjects (55%) that affect labour employability especially in the modern technology-driven labour market. However, most of workers studied in English medium school education (95%), and they mostly choose their subject of study with their self-interest (81%). English knowledge and English communication intrinsic skill enhance their labour employability. In the city, many NE people initially migrated primarily for education (36%) and after completion of their education they started seeking for a job. As such some people were reluctant to return to their native place owing to the available employment opportunities in the city or unemployment issues at the origin of migration.

Migrant workers originated mostly from urban areas (65%) that were relatively better off people in terms of education and financial condition. Some of them were forward migrants from across places outside NE States. The migrant workers include recent migrants and who have stayed in Bengaluru for over two decades revealing NE migration for work in the city is a decade old phenomenon.

Half of them have voluntarily migrated by their own decision (50%) and the rest half have involuntarily migrated as their migration decision was made by parents, husband, uncle, sibling or employer. Their migration was due to the lack of education and employment opportunities at the origin. Most workers migrated in Bengaluru initially for work (61%), some of them for education (36%) and few for other reasons such as marriage (1%). Among the migrants for work, their job aspirations were not met at their origin of migration. Migrants have a great tendency to continue migration to achieve their job aspirations. Migration for education was a second prominent reason. After completion of their studies, they continue to stay back in the city and entered in the labour market that shows the city's educational training enables NE migrants to be employable.

Concerning the features of employer, it was heterogeneous in nature. Employers consisted of both from within the state of Karnataka and elsewhere places who have lived in Bengaluru for up to 26 years. Out of the 16 employers, majority of them were males (62.5%) and the rest were females (37.5%). They were in the age between 29 and 65 years of age with a qualification ranging from pre-university, MBA to PhD in natural science. A considerable share of them (38%) has management educational

background that enables them to either establish an establishment or engage as a recruiter. However, management degree alone did not determine for instituting an establishment. Establishments include hotel and restaurant, retail, corporate, educational institution, salon and spa, and dental clinic. These are all private establishments. Most employers, rather recruiters, (63%) were working as a human resource manager in these establishments.

These establishments or employers have been employing workers for a period of up to two decades. Some of them were almost fresher and others well-experienced people in their profession of recruitment or being an employer. The size of the workers in an establishment ranges from as low as 10 workers to 2000 workers. In some establishments, most of its workers were from South India or from North East India, and in another establishment majority of workers were from elsewhere India excluding the South and North East India. The number of job applicants and workers from NE India was significant in many (63%) of these establishments.

Job Search Method

NE migrant people got job vacancy information or advertisement mostly through social networks (70%), as shown in Table 1, from friends, colleagues, social media, seniors, teachers and relatives indicating the latter have facilitated in obtaining the jobs of the migrant workers. The findings of Livingston (2006) that social networks, which supplements publicly available information, provide employment information faster than non-network job-seeking methods is still valid for the NE migrant workers too. Social network members provided information that facilitated the performance in the job search and finding a job among the NE migrant workers. Similar to Davern's (1999) social networks have been extensively used by the NE job seekers to find a job. It is also used by employers to acquire information concerning potential employees (Davern, 1999). Social networks share information on employment opportunities and provide material assistance during the job search (Banerjee, 1983) is expected from the NE migrants as well.

Workers do not know the wages associated with job vacancies but they have information about the general shape of the wage offer distribution that facilitates their search behaviour (Banerjee & Bucci, 1995). However, surprisingly, the majority of the workers (80%) claimed that they did not know the exact salary as employers did not divulge the salary either in the advertisement or verbally perhaps to strengthen the employer's wage bargaining power. Few workers have come across mentioning salary in the job vacancy information from various sources largely from advertisement, agents etc.

The employers have advertised job vacancies information through various medium of a combination of advertisement, social media, job agents, colleague, and others. Almost corroborating to the workers' observations and experiences, many employers (63%) casually advertised job vacancies likely to have a greater bargaining power of salary and other terms with the job applicants; other employers (37%) made a detailed advertisement by mentioning salary and other employment terms and conditions to restrict the number of applicants whose expected salary lies within the offered salary ambit.

Table 1: Distribution (%) of NE migrant workers classified by source of and salary mentioned in the job vacancy information

Source of job vacancy information		Monthly salary mentioned in the job vacancy			
		Yes	No	No idea	Total
Advertisement		30.8	10.5	3.3	12.9
Brokers		--	0.7	--	0.4
Agents/Organization		17.3	5.6	3.3	7.5
Placement		3.8	2.1	3.3	2.7
Consultancies		9.6	2.1	--	3.1
Direct enquiry in the store		--	1.4	11.7	3.5
Social network	All	38.5	77.6	78.3	69.8
	Friends	28.8	58.7	53.3	51.4
	Colleagues	3.8	9.1	10.0	8.2
	Social media	3.8	5.6	--	3.9
	Cousin	--	1.4	1.7	1.2
	Seniors	--	0.7	3.3	1.2
	Aunty	--	0.7	1.7	0.8
	Aunt's friend	--	0.7	--	0.4
	Professor/teacher	1.9	--	1.7	0.8
	Sister's friend	--	0.7	--	0.4
others	--	--	6.7	1.6	
All (No.)		100.0 (52)	100.0 (143)	100.0 (60)	100.0 (255)

Note: — Not available (hereafter).

Source: Field Study (Bengaluru), 2018.

The mode of seeking for a job is simpler unlike in the organised public sector since most of the workers were in retail, corporate and hospitality sectors in private sectors. The process of seeking and selection varies across workers and type of work. The workers largely got their job through only interview (72%). Social networks play a vital role in the job search process. Thus the nature, mode and extent of job-seeking behaviour and the simplicity of the recruitment process determine labour employability. Nevertheless, the labour markets condition is often associated with uncertainties of imperfect knowledge of individual characteristics, the quality of schooling and imperfect information of future demand and supply of labour as a result employers have to make a recruitment decision in a condition of uncertainty (Cai, 2013). Many workers did not receive a written job appointment or offer letter before joining for work; but most employers' have claimed of issuing it. Some workers maintained a good professional rapport with their employer and colleague that enhances the chance of labour retention and employability.

The method of selection of workers was not uniform across all the employers or establishments. Interview along with referral, resume or invitation appeared to be the most (94%) prominent features in the recruitment process. Other systems of a selection of it include referral, written and or interview. Workers usually tend to refer others who have similar potential and skill to themselves, or well-qualified candidates to safeguard referral's reputation (Montgomery, 1991).

In terms of job competitiveness, majority of the labour of current workers were employable at ease because 32% of workers had only few competitors and 24% of them had no competitor during their job interview. And many workers (29%) were employable in the very competitive labour market as they faced their job interview with many competitors. Their employability issue relates to the intensity of competitiveness while seeking for a job. Following Wittekind, Raeder and Grote (2010) NE migrant labour employability was not only determined by the job-related qualifications but also by the knowledge and information of the labour market.

Moreover, according to employer, the level of job-seeking competition was low mainly owing to the private establishments in retail, hotel, and restaurant among others in Bengaluru. It partly safeguards labour employability which is driven by a frequent job change embedded features of private sector establishments.

Job Waiting Period and Flexibility

Most of the NE migrant workers do not wait for a long period to get their present jobs largely because of the use of social networking extensively in the job search processes. The worker's average waiting period for a job was two months indicating that they obtained a job within a short period owing to their skill possession or flexibility in choosing their job that is sometimes exerted by economic pressure. The poor with low level of skill will compel the unemployed to accept and take up job as they cannot afford to remain unemployed for long period (Mitra & Verick, 2013). Workers sought for their present job for a period up to one and a half years. It shows the existence of long term unemployment, a relatively long period of over seven months (Krueger, Cramer & Cho, 2014),.problem. In India, majority of the unemployed were long term unemployed, for seven month or more, who were either not employable or did not trade down their job expectation immediately; while unemployment for a period up to six months was visible but not very prominent. About 91% of the entire NE workers got their current job within a short period of three months (Table 2). The rest waited for their current job for a longer period. They waited for their aspired job that was expected to yield some job satisfaction since they were educated. The waiting period varies between persons with the level, nature and type of educational qualification (Prasad, 1979; Visaria, 1998). Similar to the findings of Calvó-Armengol and Jackson (2004) the probability of obtaining a job decreases with the increase in the period of seeking for job among some NE migrant workers.

NE migrants mostly possess the characteristics of employability or are flexible and adjustable depending on the prevailing labour market condition. The waiting period is short because most of the workers (64%) did not seek a specific job while seeking their present job. They were not waiting for a particular job but were seeking multiple job options and waited to choose the job that suited best to their interest and skill. Thus, flexibility is very much associated with the NE migrant labour employability. Flexible workers who do not seek for a specific job obtained a job relatively easier and faster than those who sought for a particular job. The remaining share of workers sought for a specific job. Aspiring and seeking for a specific job take a longer period for getting it. Educated people mostly aspire for specific or

Table 2: Percentage share of NE migrant workers' duration of job waiting period by gender and type of seeking and workers

Job seeking or waiting duration (months)	Gender		Seeking for specific job		Current job		Total
	Male	Female	No	Yes	First	Not first	
1	50.4	47.6	53.1	41.9	43.8	51.4	49.0
2	27.1	28.6	25.3	32.3	20.0	31.4	27.8
3	14.0	14.3	14.2	14.0	22.5	10.3	14.1
4	3.9	7.1	4.9	6.5	8.8	4.0	5.5
5	0.8	0.8	0.6	1.1	1.3	0.6	0.8
6	2.3	0.8	1.2	2.2	1.3	1.7	1.6
7	--	0.8	--	1.1	1.3	--	0.4
14	0.8	--	0.6	--	--	0.6	0.4
18	0.8	--	--	1.1	1.3	--	0.4
Total (No.)	129	126	162	93	80	175	255

Source: Field Study (Bengaluru), 2018.

white-collar or organised sector job (Callaway & Bettenhausen, 1973; Roberts, 1985; Visaria, 1998; Parthasarathy & Nirmala, 2000) was not universally true particular for the NE migrant workers.

Some workers (21%) have sought jobs through competitive examinations mainly for the organised public sector job. They were mostly (96%) having educational qualification of graduate and above showing that higher educational qualification is positively associated with the public sector job aspirations. The failure of educational system to bridge the graduates with the employers and or to produce employable labour (Watson, 1983; Roberts, 1985) remains applicable for the NE migrants.

According to the employers, majority of the workers have previous work experiences. In some establishment (44%), applicants were mostly fresher, and most establishment (56%) applicants were mostly experienced candidates in their same occupation or few applicants were experienced in different occupations. Most of the employers (69%) prefer to employ experienced workers than a fresher because experienced workers have employable skills and employers wish to conserve money and time for on the job training. None of the employers exclusively show a preference of fresher over experienced workers that suppress the opportunity for the new labour supply as employers are dubious about the skills of fresher.

As much as 175 workers (68.6%) of the total workers have worked experienced from elsewhere and now employed in the current job. Among them majority (68.0%) have a job break before joining in their current job for a period up to four years showing most of the current workers did not continuously work. Nevertheless, the majority of them (85%) got their current job within six months implying they have required skill for their aspired job and are employable. Some workers (15%) have a longer period for six months or more of a break between previous and current jobs but were also employable as they re-entered into the labour market in due course of time. They formed the long term unemployed. Usually, the long term unemployed,

like these NE migrant workers, have a lower probability of finding a job, because of skill erosion or employer's discrimination against them, than the short term unemployed (Sinfield, 1967; Budd, Levine & Smith, 1988; Schmitt & Jones, 2012; Krueger, Cramer & Cho, 2014). Moreover, similar to findings of Barnes (1975) and Stephenson (1976), for NE migrant workers, lengthier the period of waiting for job, lower was their expected (reservation) wage.

As the period break between the jobs increases the proportion of persons who have previously worked decreases almost consistently indicating that some NE migrant workers were very much employable, some traded down their job expectation or employable at a lower-ranked job. This situation is corroborating with the findings of Roberts (1985), Todaro (1991) and Mitra and Verick (2013) that the long-term unemployed often compromise their job aspiration and trade down to accept the lower graded job. And others remain voluntarily unemployed for a longer period being financed from savings of the previous job or employable at a lower profiled job but did not trade down their expectation.

Unemployability or inadequacy of job opportunity appears to be a secondary issue for many NE migrant workers in the city of Bengaluru. Some NE people (31%) are employable in the occupation where they sought for a job and obtained it but they were reluctant to join in it primarily because of low remuneration. They belonged to a relatively affluent family. Also, it is because of certain reservations mainly regarding remuneration or wage; but not because of unemployable labour. Most of them (76%) had previous work experienced signalling that those who have work experienced have a higher tendency of declining a job if job expectation such as remuneration and working environment is unmet; rather than labour unemployability.

In contrast to workers, slightly more than half (56%) of the employers expressed that job applicants including fresher and experienced worker sought for a specific job; and the rest of them felt that these applicants did not seek for a particular job. The former type of applicants includes applicants having some reservation on the job, aspiration of certain job goal and trigger by previous job experiences. The latter type of applicants includes desperate job seekers, having inadequate employable skills, the inexperience of work, unspecific job aspiration, possesses a various skill for a different job, job scepticism, and pessimistic about getting a particular job that attributes to labour employability. Fresher also sought some specific job corresponding to their educational qualification and have job aspiration, but they were more open to the various employment avenues. On the contrast, experienced workers mostly inclined towards and sought for a specific job owing to their previous employment experienced and possessed job skill for furthering labour employability.

Experienced workers tend to seek a job that is similar if not higher to their previous job profile at least in terms of remuneration. Some of them got salary protection of the previous job as employers found the required skills for a given job mostly from experienced workers. Despite the request for salary protection among the experienced workers, less than half (47%) of the employers have protected the salary of previous employment for some workers. The protected salary level was either at par or exceeding with the prevailing salary rate of the establishment.

Some workers (14%) possessed qualification in excess to the prescribed for the given job highlighting that they have traded down their job aspiration below their acquired qualification, and were not employable in a job that commensurate to their acquired qualification. This raises a question on the concept of labour employability postulated by Chen and Lim (2012) that employability is the ability to get sustainable employment that commensurate with their educational qualification. Among these workers, 27% have sought a specific job and the remaining majority (73%) did not seek for a specific job which means they were ready to take up any job of their interest. However, majority of employers (63%) felt that there were some job applicants who have a different qualification (subject) from the prescribed qualification (subject). Employers felt that most job applicants either have a higher educational qualification or different subject from the prescribed subject. It creates the problem for some of the applicants who may have a higher expected wage rate and for some whose labour may be unemployable. Thus, many employers have raised the educational qualification of the workers to be employable in their establishments; others employ workers having the prescribed qualification. Thus, prescribed educational qualification is a necessary condition; and higher qualification is not an essential condition to determine labour as employable. Such situation has been established by Blaug, Layard and Woodhall (1969) and Todaro (1991) that employers have been upgrading the minimum hiring educational qualification for a job in a widespread and persistent manner.

Employability Skills

Employability is the set of skills and abilities necessary to find a job, remain in a job, doing well on a job or obtain a new job in the labour market (Tseng, 1972; Hodge, 1973; Grip, Loo & Sanders, 2004; McQuaid & Lindsay, 2005; Crossman & Clarke, 2010; Wittekind, Raeder & Grote, 2010; Misra & Mishra, 2011; Chen & Lim, 2012; Likhitkar, 2016). The perception of labour employability for a prospective employee and employer depends upon employment-related traits such as morale, motivation, performance, reliability, effectiveness, aspirations, biases and attitudes towards the employment of a person (Bricout & Bentley, 2000). Employability is about having the capability to gain initial employment, maintain employment and obtain new employment with a set of skill, knowledge and experience. It is a construct of attributes that enhance the opportunity of getting employment such as individual qualities, occupation-related and specific skills, labour market conditions, government policies, wage policies, employer training policies, etc (Grip, Loo & Sanders, 2004; Misra & Mishra, 2011). Personal attributes on employability include loyalty, commitment, honesty and integrity, enthusiasm, reliability, personal presentation, common sense, positive self-esteem, sense of humour, balanced attitude towards work life and home life, ability to deal with pressure, motivation and adaptability (Likhitkar, 2016). However, employability includes both individual quality and market conditions that limit the accessibility of some people to some jobs (Hodge, 1973).

NE migrants appear to be attracted and have higher employability trait in the occupations of retail executive or manager, teacher, security, corporate, banking, and hospitality among others. The workers were mostly employed in private sector (97%)

indicating that employability in public sector is a major issue and challenge or could not afford to continue in job search and wait for a longer period due to economic pressure. The acquirement of a conventional educational degree in the subject of arts by most of the workers and lack of preparedness and unaffordability of coaching fees for a competitive public job has hindered their level of employability in public sector. Labour unemployability is partially due to the existing educational system having an excessive theoretical bias that eventually failed to produce employable persons (Prasad, 1979; Watson, 1983; Visaria, 1998) remains true for the NE migrants too. Development of skill training or apprenticeship programme would enhance the labour employability (ILO, 2013; Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship, 2015) that necessitates NE migrants to embrace it.

Most NE migrant workers (75%) felt that they were employable and competent to work in their current job as they have confidence, skills, ability, work experience and qualification. These attributes of a worker corroborates with the individual qualities for labour employability listed by Hodge (1973), Bricout and Bentley (2000) and Likhitkar (2016). The required skills for the current job reflecting the employer's demand from workers were many and different across work such as communication, teamwork, confidence, work safely, responsibility, positive attitude, pressure management skill, initiative, planning, guidance, appreciating, adaptation, negotiation, organisational, thinking, technological, resilience, willingness to learn, self-management, motivate others, problem-solving, valuing diversity and differences, numeracy or maths knowledge and patience. Communication was the foremost and most common skill required followed by the ability to guide and having the skill to take any responsibility for their current job for majority of them (Table 3). A worker having good communication skill along with other job-related skills enhances the labour employability. Labour employability was affected by intrinsic skills such as communication, professionalism or organisational as well as by exogenous factors such as remuneration and working environment.

Workers mostly have all skills that were required, desired and demanded by their employers. Inadequacy of a specific skill does not deter them to participate for work and does not mean labour is unemployable. Existing educational syllabus and system is inadequately supplying the skill and knowledge that are needed for work and are demanded by the employer. Labour is employable and enhances it after the labour is tried and tested on the job. On the job training builds the capacity and ability to perform an activity and stay on the job. It is primarily a necessary condition for strengthening employable labour. Most workers (97%) wanted to upskill through training to raise labour productivity and employability and to achieve their aspired job.

Moreover, similar to the findings of Bricout and Bentley (2000), employers determine the labour employability and or the competency of an employee based on various factors such as communication skill, confident, attitude, flexibility, creativity, other skills, and work experiences among others. The employer demanded communication skill most prominently followed by a willingness to learn, self-motivation, flexibility, willingness to listen, confidence, professionalism, self-

Table 3: Percentage distribution of each skill needed opined by NE migrant workers in the total classified by gender and by first or otherwise job

Needed skill	Gender			Current job	
	Male	Female	Person	First	Not first
Communication	87.6	91.3	89.4	90.0	89.1
Initiative	12.4	16.7	14.5	20.0	12.0
Team work	26.4	27.8	27.1	33.8	24.0
Planning	25.6	27.0	26.3	25.0	26.9
Guidance	46.5	50.0	48.2	42.5	50.9
Confidence	31.0	37.3	34.1	32.5	34.9
Appreciating	21.7	23.0	22.4	25.0	21.1
Adaptation	17.8	23.0	20.4	20.0	20.6
Negotiation	6.2	9.5	7.8	7.5	8.0
Organisational	31.0	37.3	34.1	33.8	34.3
Thinking	10.1	11.1	10.6	13.8	9.1
Technological	27.1	26.2	26.7	33.8	23.4
Work safely	9.3	4.8	7.1	8.8	6.3
Responsibility	48.8	38.9	43.9	45.0	43.4
Positive attitude	29.5	33.3	31.4	33.8	30.3
Resilience	4.7	6.3	5.5	3.8	6.3
Willingness to learn	18.6	23.0	20.8	18.8	21.7
Self management	18.6	18.3	18.4	21.3	17.1
Motivate others	13.2	10.3	11.8	11.3	12.0
Problem solving	14.7	11.9	13.3	11.3	14.3
Pressure management	15.5	19.0	17.3	11.3	20.0
Valuing diversity and differences	17.8	25.4	21.6	18.8	22.9
Numeracy or maths	7.8	5.6	6.7	8.8	5.7
Patience	2.3	0.8	1.6	2.5	1.1

Note: Number of males: 129; Females: 126; Total: 255.

Source: Field Study (Bengaluru), 2018.

management, valuing diversity, and positive attitude among others from the job seekers. Employers demanded a different set of skills from job seekers depending on the nature and requirement of the establishment. Employers felt that workers mostly have set of skills that were required for the given job at the time of interview and or entry in the job. Contrary to this, in India, employers are facing the problem of skill gap that is essentially the difference between the skills needed for the job and its possession by the person (Likhitkar, 2016). Also, employers opined that workers acquired their skill from education, self-learning, work experience, workplace, on or off the job training, and colleague.

Occupation and Income

Migrants need employment for their livelihood and income that in turn contributes to the local economy (IOM, 2015). As such the NE migrants were working in various occupations in retail, BPO, spa, airline, educational institutions, corporate sector, IT, security service, restaurant, hospital, and bank among others for their livelihood as well as contributing to the economy of Bengaluru. They have been working in their

present job as a fresher and old-timer for varying years. Most of them worked in the private organised sector (97%) and they claimed to have a permanent job that allows them to continue to work till superannuation. They worked in organised sector because they are educated. This shows that the educated person seek job mainly in organised sector (Parthasarathy & Nirmala, 2000) remains relevant. Many migrant workers (19%) usually do not continue in their same job for a long period. They keep on changing their job irrespective of whether they are educated or otherwise owing to job insecurity or job dissatisfaction. It is also one of the challenges to get a stable employment. Unfortunately, many of them (44%) do not enter any job agreement between them and their employers that appeared to be the major reason for job insecurity and job change.

According to all the employers, their establishments have appointed and employed a worker from NE India indicating that employers in Bengaluru do not discriminate workers based on regions. Equitable employment opportunities, based on skills, knowledge and experience of a worker, are available and delivered for both males and females in almost all the establishments in Bengaluru. All employers opined that NE people incline to work or are relatively more employable in retail, corporate, salon, spa, makeup art, music institution, and hotel and restaurant as their participation are prominent in it.

In average, a worker earns a modest income of Rs.25001 to 30000 per month. Salespersons in the retail sector and security personnel earn the lowest salary. Conversely, retail manager, teachers, the human resource manager and corporate executives including BPO and IT employees earn the highest salary. The level of earnings varies across and even within occupations depending on their educational qualifications, experiences and skills. Highly educated people have earned relatively more than the lesser educated due to the differences in their acquired and possessed skill and knowledge. Almost half of the migrant workers got their expected salary, and the other half of them received salary lesser than their expectation. The latter include those who have traded down their job aspiration and salary expectation after a spell of unemployment and financial difficulty.

Job Mobility and Security

The job change is well associated with the increase in job instability (Bernhardt, Morris, Handcock & Scott, 1999) or job dissatisfaction due to low wage or working environment issues. Indeed, the worker's willingness to change a job, i.e. job search while on the job, in the labour market determines its labour employability (Wittekind, Raeder & Grote, 2010). As such many NE migrant workers (69%) keep on changing their job revealing they do not have a steady and secure job or aspire for higher remuneration. Changing a job is the mechanism by which workers generate wage growth (Bernhardt, Morris, Handcock & Scott, 1999; Even & Macpherson, 2003) is also valid for the NE migrants. For the NE migrant workers an intra change of occupation was more common than inter change of it. It indicates some workers possessed skills relevant for a job that was earlier unexplored or develops skills through work experience that eventually enhances labour employability. Further, it shows

that there was untapped employable knowledge and skills among some NE migrant workers that was ascertained only after tried and tested of their skills in some job. The skills, expertise and knowledge confine around their previous occupation hinders for inter change of occupation for the majority of the NE migrant workers in the city. The workers have a very high tendency of changing their job owing to social networks, flexibility, job insecurity, working environment, remuneration, work timing and other issues. It also indicates the availability of job opportunities and job information in the city. Similar to the findings of Wegener (1991) job changes depend on the strength of social network of a NE migrant job seeker. Flexibility in choosing job and labour employability is a prominent reason perhaps essentially for intra job change or mobility. Majority of them (89%) have gained work experiences from Bengaluru itself. Experienced workers were relatively more employable.

Hence, intra and inter occupational change or mobility prevails. The former enhances labour employability and increases the chance of getting employment when compared to the latter. However, inter occupational mobility is challenging and not very easy as perceived. NE migrant workers having the lowest on the job satisfaction mostly change both their current job and occupation that is corroborating with the findings of Wright & Bonett (1992) and Wright & Huang (2012).

Some workers (9%) tend to often change their job after working for a certain period in a job. Some people regularly change their job owing to various employment-related traits mainly for higher remuneration, secured job, better career prospects and desire for a permanent job among other reasons.

Worker's changing employment is the mechanism to bargain a higher salary than their previous job salary with the employer. The skilled workers in particular have a wage bargaining power (Cahuc, Vinay & Robin, 2006) was also experienced by the NE migrant workers. Worker's acceptance or decline to the offered salary and their job preference also determined the degree of labour employability. Meanwhile, all employers do maintain and follow a salary structure for different types of workers having a different set of skill, experience and qualification. Nevertheless, workers often expressed and negotiated their expected monthly salary within or even beyond the prevailing salary offer limit during the job interview. Most employers (81%) do have experienced that many of their workers usually change their job for want of higher remuneration. Importantly, in India, employment instability or mobility is partly owing to the employers' policies of constantly changing the workforce to maintain low wage bills (Papola, 1968). However, most of the employers in Bengaluru were rigid in offering the wage. Some workers declined the offered wage and refused to join in the job due to unmet job expectation in the respective establishment or got their expected job elsewhere.

Majority of the jobs of NE migrants are insecure and temporary irrespective of their claim of holding a permanent job. Many workers (69%) tend to leave their job voluntarily when dissatisfied or involuntarily when the establishment is closed or employers lay off after certain years of employment. Most workers (56%) in Bengaluru left their previous job largely due to low remuneration and working environment problem.

The nature of employments claimed by workers were mostly permanent (61%), followed by a temporary (32%) and contractual (7%) job. Similarly, the nature of job offered by the employers were mostly permanent (75%) and the rest were temporary (12.5%) and contractual (12.5%). The permanent job is relatively more secured and stabled job than the other two. Job security is ensured by the job agreement entered mutually between the worker and employer. Majority of the employers (88%) claimed to have entered the job agreement before worker joins for work. However, the extent of it was much greater and not corresponding with the claimed of workers from NE India. Only 56% of workers have job agreement and the rest did not have it that cause job insecurity. Further, most of the employers (81%) provide a probationary period of employment to test the skills, professionalism and other work-related skills of a worker. Majority of the workers (87%) had received on the job training largely at workplace and from elsewhere place. Also, all employers claimed to have provided a free on the job training mostly at the workplace and some at elsewhere place to their workers irrespective of their temporary, contractual or permanent position. Job training is inevitable for any workers for the acquirement of working skills or enhancement of skills.

Job Dissatisfaction and On-the-Job Search

Employers invest in employees and compensate them for their lost opportunity cost by providing further skill investment and employment stability; while employees voluntarily agree to remain with that employer to allow the employer to earn returns from such skill investment in employees (Burea, 2003). Thus, majority of the NE migrant workers (81%) want to keep and stay on their current job owing to job satisfaction, pleasant working environment, remunerative, the professionalism of co-workers, and other reasons. According to Mitchell, Holtom, Lee, Sablynski & Erez (2001), many non-financial and non-attitudinal factors place people in networks of forces that keep workers in their jobs. The attitudinal factors such as job satisfaction and organisational commitment have negative relationships with labour turnover. Job retention essentially and eventually leads to up-skilling to enhance labour employability. It relates to the commitment of workers and attainment of job expectancies. However, some current NE workers (19%) want to leave their present job mainly due to low remuneration. Employee being embedded in an organisation is associated with reduced intent to leave and reduced the actual rate of leaving from the job (Mitchell, Holtom, Lee, Sablynski & Erez, 2001). Similar to Wright & Bonett (1992) and Wright & Huang (2012) the NE workers having low in job satisfaction were much more likely to leave their job.

These workers who want to continue in it or leave it include both new labour entrants and experienced workers. Among those workers who want to continue in their current job, 27% were on their first job as new labour and the rest 73% were on their second or subsequent job. Similarly, among workers who want to discontinue from their current job, 52% were in there first job and the remaining (48%) in their subsequent job. Workers wishing to leave it reveal the prevalence of workers with higher job and salary expectation. Their continuance in their current job despite a desire to quit from their current job with their acquired qualification and limited

skills portrays the difficulty in getting a new job. It denotes that their labour is currently unemployable in an occupation other than their current occupation and higher salaried job.

Some (20%) of the current workers sought a new job while they were on-the-job, as a job mobility strategy, owing to job dissatisfaction. Similar to the findings of Spencer (1986) NE migrant workers searching for alternative employment while on-the-job was an attempt to exit from a dissatisfying work situation. Job dissatisfaction that is primarily caused by being low-skilled, insecure and having low remuneration has motivated on-the-job search (Kim, 2010). The level of on-the-job search depends on the alternative wage a worker expects to elicit and a worker's asking wage (Banerjee & Bucci, 1995). Among on-the-job searchers, some (31%) were ready to quit their current job and join in the new job if they obtain it; otherwise will remain in their current job. And the rest workers (69%) were extremely dissatisfied with their current job who might leave their current job soon even if they do not find a new job that may be due to financial or attitudinal factors or otherwise. Current workers who were seeking for a new job sought for a period of up to two years primarily because of wanting a stable, decent and more remunerative job. It reveals their current level of unemployability in their aspired new job. Their labour employability could be enhanced through work experience and training.

Meanwhile, majority of the employers (88%) felt that their employees were satisfied with their job owing to a remunerative job, pleasant working environment, regular salary, no bias attitude of the employer, pleasant working hour, and social security benefits among other reasons. However, all employers have experienced that some employee has left their job by giving quit notice to them primarily for seeking a more remunerative job. Employer's attribution of worker's job satisfaction to remunerative job and workers quitting their job for seeking a greater remunerative job implies the employer's inability to meet the persistently increasing remuneration expectation of the workers.

The level of employee retention depends on the health of the organisation (Wright & Huang, 2012) and organisational culture values (Sheridan, 1992). Critical information on employees' perceptions of the organizational characteristics enables employee retention (Spencer, 1986). According to Spencer (1986) if there are many mechanisms for employee to voice their job dissatisfaction then the retention rate of employees is high. But most importantly, job performance highly determines employees' retention (Holzer, Stoll & Wissoker, 2004). However, in Bengaluru, all employers want to retain their current employees in various extents primarily owing to labour productivity and satisfactory work performance. All employers felt that some or most of their employees will continue with their current job largely because of remunerative nature of the job, pleasant working environment and professionalism of their co-workers. On the contrary, majority (88%) and few (12%) of the employers felt some and most of their workers respectively would leave their current job mainly owing to low remuneration, unpleasant working environment, job dissatisfaction, inconvenience in commutation, and co-worker unprofessionalism among others.

Workers usually use their creativity while performing their job in their workplace for which their employer gives some incentives in the form of acknowledgement and

award. Majority (81.2%) of the workers have received some sort of appreciation and reward for their work creativity from their employers in the form of monetary, certificate of appreciation, verbal appreciation, promotion or salary increment. The remaining workers (18.8%) felt that they were neither acknowledged nor awarded with monetary benefit, certificate or in promotion for their creative work performance. Majority of the employers (87%) acknowledges and bestow rewards to their workers when they have executed work with certain creativity at their workplace in the form of verbal acknowledgement, incentives as a monetary reward, certificate of acknowledgement, and even in promotion for their career in various establishments. To some extent, it is to ensure the worker's satisfaction and eventually for retention of a worker.

Job Problem and Resolution

At workplace, majority (98%) of the NE migrant workers have faced one or numerous types of problems ranging from an arrogant customer, communication, adaptation, harassment, technical, rotational work shift to the working environment. Such problems do not prevent them from work participation but helps in the improvement of their skills and enhances the level of employability. These problems are some of the challenges faced by the migrants that need to be tackled amicably through discussion. The problems of most of the workers were addressed and solved by colleagues or co-workers (60%). Some workers solve the problem by themselves (20%), employer (19%) and also job trainer (1%). Thus, co-workers, trainers and employers were largely and mutually cordial, dependent, and supportive to each another at the workplace.

Also, all employers have faced various kinds of problems from the workers including issues on work ethic, attitude, indiscipline, and arrogance among others. Employers ease the problem commonly through an amicable discussion to resolve the issue. As per the employers, similar to the response of workers, if workers encounter a problem at the workplace the worker themselves, colleagues, employer and trainer solve the problem at individual capacity or collectively. The workers, co-workers, employers and trainers mutually depend and help one another to ensure that labour remains employable and workplace conducive.

The entry in and exit from a job were very casual. Some workers left their job without submitting a resignation letter in establishments such as retail, corporate, hotel and restaurant, music institute and salon and spa. Again employers attributed it primarily to seek a more remunerative job. Further, majority of the employers (81%) have terminated some of their employees after serving the termination notice owing to the issue of lack of professionalism, arrogance, health issue, incapable of pressure management, irregular in attendance, and unproductive among others that were mostly related to the factors of labour employability. Few employers also terminate some workers without serving any termination notice as a worker violated their company's rules, arrogant, health issue, or leave provision. The offered nature of the job, i.e. mostly permanent with job terms and conditions agreement, did not corroborate with the termination of job outcome.

Majority (72%) of the workers gave feedback related to their work to the employer mainly related to office management, working environment, salary or incentives, the technology used in their office, proper planning for work and motivation to the workers. They provided feedback prominently and commonly on management, working environment and salary including incentives that demonstrated that workers envisage alleviating it to a better condition. In line with Spencer (1986) the more an organization facilitates workers the opportunity to voice dissatisfaction over their work, as problem resolution mechanism, in order to change dissatisfying work the greater is employee retention. Further, employers may need to consider employees' efforts to change an unsatisfactory work situation to remain in the job. Meanwhile, the rest workers (28%) did not give any feedback to their employer because of either there was no feedback system, they do not want to give it or employer did not ask for it despite existing feedback system at their workplace.

The workers and employers relation can be elevated through mutual discussion as well as a feedback system. Majority of the employers (63%) received feedback from their employees on management, working environment, responsibility, incentives, leave, work pressure, professionalism, motivation, and salary among others. An employer may even attribute it to unemployable labour when a worker outspoken and transgress the decision of the employer.

Conclusions

It is evident that the NE migrants prominently use social networks as a platform to find their job. Job vacancies were largely advertised in a casual manner that disadvantages the workers and advantages the employers in wage bargaining. The process of recruitment was only through job interview for majority of the workers owing to the nature of establishment specifically private sector. Jobs are not very competitive because of flexibility in entry and exit in the private sector establishments such as retail or hospitality. The average waiting period for job was very short (two months) for the NE migrant workers particularly due to the flexibility in searching and choosing job. Indeed there were also people who sought for a specific job with certain reservation wage particularly among the experienced workers. Long term unemployment i.e. long waiting period was also prevalent. Most of the employers show a preference to employ experienced over fresher worker. Many workers do not have a continuous work that is a major concern relating to job security, labour employability and job satisfaction. Previous job salary was not always protected in the new job. Some workers have lowered their job aspiration below their educational qualification meanwhile employers have raised the minimum hiring qualification of the workers to be employable in their establishment due to the problem of skill gap that is the shortfall of skill required by the employer and the skill possessed by the worker. The attributes of labour employability of workers and employers primarily include communication, ability, responsibility, flexibility and experience among others specifically in retail, corporate and hospitality establishments. Communication is the foremost skills required and demanded for executing their job and for labour to be employable. Labour employability is affected by intrinsic skills such as communication and exogenous factors like remuneration. For many workers, labour employability is

ensured after the labour was tried and tested on the job. Migrant workers prominently engaged in retail, hospitality and corporate job. The workers' average income was modest and earnings were not uniform across the occupation. Workers kept on changing their job in an attempt to achieve wage growth. However, the job mobility is predominantly intra occupational change. Job mobility is often associated with job dissatisfaction and organisational issues. On-the-job search for new employment due to dissatisfaction of current work condition is considerable. It is caused by financial or non-financial factor, attitudinal or non-attitudinal factor or both. Employers also expressed a similar reason for on-the-job search concern. However, majority of the workers desire to stay on their job due to job satisfaction and employer showed a desire to retain their workers owing to labour productivity. Both workers and employers encountered a widespread work, workplace and organisational problems that were addressed through various mechanisms involving colleague, employers and worker's voicing dissatisfaction.

As a policy measure, promotion of English medium education is vital to enhance employability. Acquisition of greater skill embedded educational qualification is required to enhance labour employability and to improve earnings. Building a strong social network and access adequate labour market information from various sources is needed for convenient job search and finding. Employers need to widely advertise detail job vacancy information to reduce job information asymmetry and encourage job applicants. Job searchers need to be flexible in selecting job avenues to get a job more conveniently at ease. Seek multiple job options if the acquired education or training is too general. Labour is envisaged to be tried and tested to discover the unexplored skills of labour through internship or apprenticeship. People need to consider private-sector job as good as government job. Job mobility may be encouraged for salary growth or career development. Job continuity enhances upskilling of labour intrinsic skills and labour employability. Eliminate workplace, remuneration and other issues through the adoption of adequate, proper and practical policy measures including effective discussion platform to address workers issues and labour retention. To retain and promote labour employability ensure the cordial professional relationship between workers, co-workers, employers and trainers.

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